

LEGAL REGULATION OF THE DEMOCRATIZATION OF SCHOOL PUBLIC MANAGEMENT: CONSTITUTION AND PRAXIS

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ABSTRACT

This academic study delves into the renewed role of school management in the modern era, following fundamental legal changes enacted by the 1988 Federal Constitution and the National Education Guidelines and Framework Law No. 9394/96. The research questions the importance of democratization at the school council interface and its impact on the educational environment. The work proposes to analyze the relevance of this issue using a qualitative approach, grounded in the review of relevant literature and supported by social representation theories. In the concluding section, the research underscores the Council's vital role in planning, monitoring, and evaluating daily school actions, both pedagogical and administrative-financial, aiming at the optimization of resources. It emphasizes the need for managers and teachers to continually invest in knowledge enhancement and its dissemination, to strengthen the innovative and creative capacity of educational institutions. The study concludes that the school manager, acting as a leader, should shape individuals capable of executing tasks competently, preparing them to handle the transformations resulting from the post-modern era.

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